

Failure of Osteosynthesis in a Pathological Fracture Caused by Enchondroma of the Fourth Metacarpal: Surgical Revision with Structural Bone Graft Case Report

Diego Rafael Gonzalez Ramos¹, Victor Manuel Alayon Vazquez²

¹Trauma and Orthopedics Resident. Clínica Hospital Mérida, ISSSTE. Facultad de Medicina de la Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán.

²Orthopedist. Clínica Hospital Mérida, ISSSTE.

ABSTRACT

Background: Enchondromas are benign cartilaginous tumors that frequently affect the small bones of the hand and may present with pathological fractures. The optimal management of these lesions remains debated, particularly when structural bone defects persist after curettage.

Case presentation: We present the case of a 38-year-old female with a pathological fracture of the fourth metacarpal secondary to an enchondroma. Initial treatment consisted of curettage and internal fixation with plate osteosynthesis. Although early postoperative evolution was satisfactory, the patient developed implant failure associated with persistent structural bone weakness. Revision surgery was performed with removal of the failed implant, structural tricortical bone grafting, and stable fixation.

Results: The patient evolved with progressive bone consolidation and functional recovery of the hand. This case highlights the importance of restoring structural stability in metacarpal enchondromas associated with pathological fractures, especially when significant bone defects remain after curettage.

Conclusion: Structural bone grafting may play an important role in restoring mechanical stability and preventing implant failure in metacarpal enchondromas associated with pathological fractures.

KEYWORDS: Enchondroma; Metacarpal fracture; Pathological fracture; Osteosynthesis failure; Structural bone graft

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
18 March 2026

Available On:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Enchondroma is the most common benign cartilaginous tumor of the hand and one of the most frequent primary bone tumors affecting the small tubular bones [1]. It originates from intramedullary remnants of hyaline cartilage, and its development has been widely described in classic histopathological studies [1]. In the differential diagnosis, other cartilaginous lesions must be considered, including low-grade chondrosarcoma, particularly when atypical clinical features are present [2]. In rare cases, cartilaginous tumors may be associated with conditions such as Ollier disease or may occur in unusual locations, which can complicate the differential diagnosis [3].

Radiographically, enchondroma typically appears as a well-defined intramedullary lytic lesion with cortical thinning or expansion and a chondroid matrix pattern, generally without significant periosteal reaction [4]. Many lesions are asymptomatic and detected incidentally; however, a considerable proportion may present with a pathological fracture secondary to progressive structural weakening of the bone [5,6]. Large clinical series have confirmed that pathological fracture represents one of the most frequent clinical presentations of enchondromas of the hand [7,8]. Epidemiological studies have also described a predominant distribution of these lesions in the small tubular bones of the hand, particularly in the metacarpals and phalanges [9].

Failure of Osteosynthesis in a Pathological Fracture Caused by Enchondroma of the Fourth Metacarpal: Surgical Revision with Structural Bone Graft Case Report

The management of symptomatic enchondroma is surgical. Intralesional curettage remains the standard treatment, with or without the use of bone grafting [10,11]. Some studies have reported satisfactory outcomes with simple curettage and early mobilization in selected cases without significant structural compromise [10]. Alternative techniques such as endoscopic curettage or intramedullary fixation following tumor removal have also been described with satisfactory results [12,13].

However, when enchondroma is associated with pathological fracture or significant cortical thinning, treatment must address not only tumor eradication but also restoration of the mechanical stability of the bone [6,14]. In these situations, cancellous bone graft provides biological support, although its ability to immediately restore structural resistance may be limited [11]. Biomechanical studies have demonstrated that structural filling of the defect significantly influences metacarpal strength following curettage [15].

The present report describes a case of enchondroma of the fourth metacarpal associated with pathological fracture that evolved with osteosynthesis failure despite initial locked plate fixation and was successfully treated with revision surgery and structural cortical bone graft reconstruction.

II. CLINICAL CASE

A 38-year-old right-handed female patient with no relevant past medical history presented with a diaphyseal bone mass in the fourth metacarpal of the left hand with an evolution of approximately two years. Initially, she reported mild discomfort and localized swelling.

Four months prior to definitive evaluation, she sustained a low-energy trauma, after which a pathological fracture developed at the level of the lesion. This was managed conservatively at another institution. A palpable mass measuring approximately 3 cm in diameter persisted and was painful on deep palpation.

Subsequently, after a new direct trauma to the dorsum of the left hand while attempting to move heavy objects, she developed intense pain and functional limitation of the fourth finger, prompting evaluation in the emergency department.

Anteroposterior and oblique radiographs demonstrated an intramedullary lytic lesion in the fourth metacarpal associated with a simple, transverse, complete fracture at the mid-diaphyseal third (Figures 1). Surgical treatment was indicated; however, the patient initially requested voluntary discharge, and a short arm splint was applied.

A) B)
Figure 1. Radiographs of left hand showing an intramedullary lytic lesion of the fourth metacarpal associated with a pathological fracture. A) Anteroposterior view B) Oblique view

Three days later, she accepted surgical management. A dorsal approach was performed with extensive intralesional curettage of the lesion, harvesting of autologous bone graft from the olecranon, anatomical fracture reduction, and internal fixation using a locking plate. Stability was confirmed intraoperatively with fluoroscopy. The immediate postoperative course was satisfactory, and the patient was discharged the following day (Figure 2).

A) B)
Figure 2. Radiographs after the initial surgical treatment showing anatomical reduction of the fourth metacarpal fracture after locking compression plate fixation. A) Anteroposterior view. B) Oblique view.

At 12 months of follow-up, the patient reported persistent pain. Radiographic evaluation demonstrated fatigue failure of the osteosynthesis material with plate breakage at the level of the fifth hole, a residual bone defect, and absence of complete consolidation (Figure 3).

Failure of Osteosynthesis in a Pathological Fracture Caused by Enchondroma of the Fourth Metacarpal: Surgical Revision with Structural Bone Graft Case Report

A). B)
Figure 3. Radiographs showing fatigue failure of the plate with a persistent bone defect. A) Oblique view. B) Lateral view.

Revision surgery was performed, consisting of removal of the osteosynthesis material, repeat extended curettage, biopsy sampling, and structural reconstruction using an autologous cortical graft harvested from the right proximal tibia, followed by new internal fixation with a locking plate. At 6–8 weeks of follow-up, radiographic consolidation grade Montoya 2–3 was documented with adequate graft incorporation at six months (Figure 4). The patient evolved without signs of infection or local complications, with progressive functional recovery.

A) B)
Figure 4. Radiographs after revision surgery showing reconstruction with a new locking plate fixation and graft incorporation. A) Anteroposterior view. B) Oblique view.

III. DISCUSSION

The surgical treatment of enchondroma of the hand remains a matter of debate. While simple curettage has demonstrated satisfactory outcomes in selected lesions without significant structural compromise [10], the presence of a pathological fracture modifies the biomechanical and therapeutic scenario [6].

In cases associated with fracture, the objective of treatment should include restoration of structural stability in addition to tumor resection [6]. The management of hand

enchondroma has also been described as a surgical dilemma when significant mechanical compromise exists [14].

Bone grafting following curettage improves the biological environment for bone healing [11]. Favorable results with meticulous curettage and grafting techniques have been reported, with low recurrence rates [11]. However, these series do not specifically analyze implant mechanical failure in cases with persistent cortical defects.

Tumor curettage may reduce the structural resistance of the metacarpal when the resulting bone defect is not adequately reconstructed [15]. Systematic reviews have suggested that curettage without defect filling may be sufficient in selected lesions; however, when significant cortical involvement exists, mechanical stability may be compromised [16]. Comparative studies have demonstrated differences in stability and complication rates depending on the material used to fill the bone defect [17]. In the present case, persistence of the structural metacarpal defect likely contributed to mechanical failure of the implant following the initial intervention.

In small tubular bones such as the metacarpals, which are subjected to torsional and bending forces during grasping, mechanical reconstruction becomes particularly important. Adequate stability following tumor resection is essential to prevent mechanical complications [13]. Even with minimally invasive techniques such as endoscopic curettage, appropriate case selection is crucial to avoid structural instability [12,18].

In our case, despite the initial use of a locked plate, the persistence of a significant structural defect in the fourth metacarpal likely promoted excessive load transfer to the implant and subsequent material fatigue. Several studies have emphasized that in the surgical management of benign cartilaginous tumors of the hand, implant stability largely depends on adequate restoration of the underlying bone support, particularly when cortical compromise is present [19,20].

Revision surgery with structural cortical graft allowed restoration of diaphyseal continuity and improved load distribution between bone and implant, promoting early consolidation and satisfactory functional recovery. This approach is consistent with evidence supporting the importance of structural support in tumor-related bone defects [15,17].

In this case, stable fixation alone proved insufficient; adequate structural reconstruction was necessary to restore physiological load distribution and reduce the risk of fatigue failure.

Failure of Osteosynthesis in a Pathological Fracture Caused by Enchondroma of the Fourth Metacarpal: Surgical Revision with Structural Bone Graft Case Report

IV. CONCLUSION

In this case, initial treatment with curettage, cancellous bone grafting, and internal fixation was insufficient due to the persistence of a structural bone defect, resulting in implant fatigue and nonunion. Revision surgery with structural cortical graft reconstruction restored metacarpal stability, leading to early radiographic consolidation and favorable clinical recovery.

DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT

The authors certify that the patient was informed about the use and publication of clinical information and imaging studies. Written informed consent was obtained, and the patient was informed that their name and initials would not be published, maintaining anonymity.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP

This study was conducted without external financial support. The authors declare that funding did not influence the study design, data collection, analysis, or manuscript preparation.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there were no conflicts of interest during the elaboration of this paper.

REFERENCES

- I. **Milgram JW.** The origins of osteochondromas and enchondromas. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 1983;(174):264-284. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00003086-198304000-00037>
- II. **Suster D, Hung YP, Nielsen GP.** Differential diagnosis of cartilaginous lesions of bone. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2020;144(1):71-82. <https://doi.org/10.5858/arpa.2019-0441-RA>
- III. **Ding C, Chen W, Liu F, Xiong M, Chen J.** Skull base chondrosarcoma caused by Ollier disease: a case report and literature review. *World Neurosurg.* 2019;127:103-108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2019.03.037>
- IV. **Engel H, Herget GW, Füllgraf H, Sutter R, Benndorf M, Bamberg F, et al.** Chondrogenic bone tumors: the importance of imaging characteristics. *Rofo.* 2021;193(3):262-275. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1288-1209>
- V. **Biondi N, Varacallo M.** Enchondroma. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2019. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK536938/>
- VI. **Zhou X, Zhao B, Keshav P, Chen X, Gao W, Yan H.** The management and surgical intervention timing of enchondromas: a 10-year experience. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2017;96(16):e6678. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.0000000000006678>
- VII. **Sollaci C, Rezende MU, Gracitelli ME, et al.** Enchondromas of the hand: a 20-year experience. *Rev Bras Ortop.* 2019;54(6):719-726. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0039-1697970>
- VIII. **Gaulke R.** The distribution of solitary enchondromas at the hand. *J Hand Surg Br.* 2002;27(5):444-445. <https://doi.org/10.1054/jhsb.2002.0826>
- IX. **Verdegaal SHM, Brouwers HFJ, van Zwet EW, Hogendoorn PCW, Taminiau AHM.** Low-grade chondrosarcoma of long bones treated with curettage and cryosurgery: long-term follow-up of 46 cases. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2012;94(13):1206-1212. <https://doi.org/10.2106/jbjs.j.01498>
- X. **Pietramala S, Rovere G, Ravaioli C, Mignano C, Smakaj A, Fidanza A, et al.** Surgical treatment of enchondromas of the hand: curettage only and early mobilization. *Diseases.* 2025;13(3):84. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diseases13030084>
- XI. **Georgiannos D, Lampridis V, Bisbinas I.** Phenolization and coralline hydroxyapatite grafting following meticulous curettage for the treatment of enchondroma of the hand. *Hand (N Y).* 2015;10(1):111-115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11552-014-9674-2>
- XII. **Sekiya I, Hoshi K, Koga H, Muneta T.** Treatment of enchondromas in the hand by endoscopic curettage without bone grafting. *J Hand Surg Br.* 1997;22(2):230-234. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-7681\(97\)80070-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-7681(97)80070-8)
- XIII. **Kaempf de Oliveira R, Brunelli JPF, Araújo Filho R, Aita MA, Delgado PJ.** Intramedullary fixation with cannulated screw after resection of enchondroma in the hand: technique description and case series. *J Hand Surg Glob Online.* 2023;5(4):413-420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhsg.2023.03.008>
- XIV. **Biswas G, Zafar A, Kyada M.** Enchondroma of hands: a surgical dilemma and our experience. *J Orthop Case Rep.* 2025;15(11):133-136. <https://doi.org/10.13107/jocr.2025.v15.i11.6332>
- XV. **Pianta TJ, Baldwin PS, Obopilwe E, Mazzocca AD, Rodner CM, Silverstein EA.** A biomechanical analysis of treatment options for enchondromas of the hand. *Hand (N Y).* 2013;8(1):86-93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11552-012-9476-3>
- XVI. **Bachoura A, Rice IS, Lubahn AR, Lubahn JD.** The surgical management of hand enchondroma without post-curettage void augmentation: authors' experience and a systematic review. *Hand (N Y).*

Failure of Osteosynthesis in a Pathological Fracture Caused by Enchondroma of the Fourth Metacarpal: Surgical Revision with Structural Bone Graft Case Report

- 2015;10(3):461-471.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11552-015-9738-y>
- XVII. **Nazarova NZ.** The surgical management of the cavity and bone defects in enchondromas of the hand: autograft versus substitutes. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2021;16:54.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.suronc.2021.101565>
- XVIII. **Lui TH.** Endoscopic curettage and bone grafting of the enchondroma of the proximal phalanx of the great toe. *Foot Ankle Surg.* 2015;21(2):137-141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fas.2014.06.001>
- XIX. **Gautier E, Sommer C.** Guidelines for the clinical application of the locking compression plate (LCP). *Injury.* 2003;34(Suppl 2):B63-B76.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.injury.2003.09.026>
- XX. **Satti LR, Yennapu NR, Inturi R, Surada R.** A rare occurrence of enchondroma in the head of femur in an adult male: a case report. *J Orthop Case Rep.* 2023;13(4):62-65.
<https://doi.org/10.13107/jocr.2023.v13.i04.3618>